

Supplementary Material for

CALPHAD workflow for Fe–S and Fe–S–O phase diagrams: importance of greigite stability

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Synthesis and characterization

Bulk Fe₃S₄ was synthesized by hydrothermal method and characterized by powder X-ray diffraction (PXRD). More details are provided in Subramani et al., 2020.

Differential Scanning Calorimetry

Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) experiments were performed using a Setaram Labsys EVO instrument. 23.93 mg of sample pellet was heated in an alumina crucible at the rate of 10°C/min up to 600 °C under argon atmosphere and cooled at 20°C/min. The background correction of DSC data was done by running a blank experiment using empty alumina crucible.

Powder X-Ray diffraction

Powder X-Ray diffraction (PXRD) of the final product after TG-DSC was performed using a Bruker D2 benchtop diffractometer equipped with Ni-filtered Cu K α radiation ($\lambda = 1.542 \text{ \AA}$) operating at an accelerating voltage of 30 kV and emission current of 10 mA. The data were

collected in the 2θ range of $10\text{--}100^\circ$ with a 0.018° step size and a 2 s collection time per step. The PXRD pattern was subjected to Rietveld analysis using GSAS-II software.

Fig. 1 - The four-step reproducible pipeline

A single typed provenance manifest ties the steps together: every value is read from it and stays traceable to its primary source.

Each step records typed provenance back to its primary source; packaged for reproduction - MIT-licensed.

Figure S1. The four step reproducible pipeline: (1) thermodynamic-database lookup → (2) ingestion of the greigite calorimetry, provenance tracked values from a knowledge graph manifest → (3) deterministic TDB stitching → (4) pycalphad grand potential minimization and plotting. The Gibbs energy function (TDB format) is the common data currency passed between steps, and provenance is recorded at each step.

Figure S2. Greigite heat capacity and the Debye–Einstein fit (Shumway et al., 2022, per FeS_{1.33}). The greigite heat capacity was calculated using the Debye–Einstein fit of Shumway et al. (2022): $C_p = m \cdot D(\Theta_d/T) + n \cdot E(\Theta_e/T) + AT$ where D and E are the Debye and Einstein contributions. Integration yields the thermodynamic functions, and the greigite Gibbs energy was referenced to the SGTE91 elemental functions for consistency with the rest of the database.

Figure S3. Fe–O stability diagram.

Figure S4. DSC of the original greigite sample (2020), room temperature to 880 K. Heating, solid line; cooling, dashed line.

Figure S5. Powder XRD of the product after DSC to 880 K (2020): predominantly pyrrhotite with possible trace magnetite.

Figure S6 DSC of aged greigite, performed in 2026. The cooling curve did not reach 300 K before the program was finished.

Figure S7. Powder XRD of the product after DSC to 880 K performed in 2026. The product is predominantly pyrrhotite with 10–15 wt% magnetite